

THE NEED FOR TRANSFORMATION OF BANKS WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT CONCEPT AND THE ROLE OF ESG INFORMATION

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The objective crisis events occurring in the economy, both globally and nationally, are increasing the risk of recession. Nevertheless, the strategic development direction aimed at sustainable development remains relevant. The concept of sustainable development involves the involvement of a large amount of information in business processes, which was previously not sufficiently taken into account by commercial banks. This is due to the need to apply new priorities in the areas of environmental protection, public interests and corporate governance in business activities.

These priorities are briefly expressed in many scientific studies and practical documents by the term ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance), but the content of these parameters is interpreted differently in different sources [1] (Zhirnova, 2022). In the banking sector, the collection and processing of information about the external environment (regulatory, legal and conjunctural) and the consumer behavior of its customers is a standard and mandatory functional part of the business. This, in turn, allows banks to constantly update their decisions in the face of changing business conditions.

However, the “green transformation” is creating a completely new, truly large-scale flow of information in banking. Most commercial banks are not sufficiently prepared, either organizationally or technologically, to process this information. This is one of the objective risks associated with the digital transformation of banks. A comprehensive analysis of these risks is provided in the source.[2]

Uzbek scientists B.T. Berdiyarov [4], V.A. Kotov, I.L. Butikov, N.Kh. Jumaev, O.B. Sattarov [5], O.Q. Abdurakhmanov, R.T. Tursunov, R.R. Tojiev [6] have covered the theoretical and practical aspects of the activities, tasks and development of commercial banks. Also, the issues of implementing bank marketing and financial management in the management process were discussed by A.Sh. Bekmurodov, B.Z. Mustafaev [7], B.K. Mirzamaydinov [8], M. Nasritdinova, M.M. Abdurakhmanova, etc. have found their reflection in their research. Nevertheless, the financial stability of commercial banks in the context

of globalization has not been studied in depth enough. This scientific research requires the development of theoretical views, methodological approaches and practical recommendations on these issues.

The discrepancy between the necessity, even inevitability, of bank transformation within the framework of the concept of sustainable development and the real level of readiness forms a new risk area (landscape) and, as a result, directly affects the economic security of commercial banks. The authors previously noted: “a clear connection is being formed between closely related concepts: economic security, ‘green’ economy and modernization. These categories and the processes associated with them are objectively conditioned” [3]

Credit risk is directly related to the main source of bank income and has a direct impact on the economic security of the bank in the medium term. Operational and regulatory risks, like credit risk, are an object of management in a commercial bank, but the introduction of new ESG factors into the risk management system significantly increases the complexity of the management process. Reputational risk, on the other hand, affects long-term strategic goals and is taken into account in the process of developing and implementing the bank's strategy.

The ESG data block within Big Data is rapidly developing, and by 2022 the number of parameters (data types) belonging to this group is estimated to be close to 1,000. The second problem area is the use of useful data in management (operational) processes, including predictive analysis, which previously had stable management practices. While the first problem can be solved by attracting external resources, for example, outsourcing certain functions (although there is a shortage of such resources in the market), the second zone falls under the direct and exclusive responsibility of bank management.[4]

Strategic measures to combat ESG-related risks should be aimed at eliminating the main problem - the insufficient understanding of the value of the process of taking into account new important factors by employees. This requires a stimulating effect on the bank's corporate culture. This process is essentially a planned organizational crisis and a complex form of change management. The bank should inform all employees about ESG requirements and their recognized importance by the bank. Without employee involvement, the change process may stall in daily routine operations.

It is necessary to develop a regulatory document that links the strategic sustainable development goals with the bank's tactical commercial goals,

including investments in infrastructure and other tasks within the framework of economic security. The introduction of ESG criteria into operational decision-making processes - both in assessing the impact on bank risks and in assessing the impact of the bank on ESG indicators in the external environment - creates new requirements for IT support. The initial state of the bank's IT infrastructure is adapted to current operational processes, is focused on reducing costs and is poorly adapted to receiving and processing new data. Therefore, the addition of new components to the historically formed complex IT architecture creates operational risks in the medium and long term.

These are typical risks associated with the development of a business model shaped by ESG factors, which need to be addressed. Based on an analysis of foreign experience, the following recommendations can be made.[5]

The volume and diversity of data require the use of artificial intelligence tools in developing operational decisions, which requires the formation of new competencies as part of the bank's competitive advantages. The second area, "internal banking processes," includes the following key recommendations: integrating new ESG requirements and constraints into existing processes at the management level, such as reviewing credit scoring algorithms; reviewing data processing regulations, including their content, protection, and frequency of updates; and developing plans to integrate ESG policies, such as procedures for obtaining "green" certificates for investments.[6]

The inclusion of ESG data in the business processes of a bank's management directly affects its economic security, as it requires a significant increase in the complexity of operational processes. This situation affects the profitability of certain operations and the level of operational risks. At the same time, the need for machine processing of large volumes of poorly structured data creates an additional burden on the information infrastructure and leads to an increase in operating costs.

The main principles of introducing ESG data into the management processes of a commercial bank are outlined in the form of recommendations within the framework of three problem areas of business process management identified by the authors. Special recommendations have been developed in this article for a relatively new problem - the growth of technical debt.

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